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THE ROLE OF SONGS AND POEMS IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The article considers the role of songs and poems in English lessons in the elementary classes. It is difficult to imagine teaching English without methodical approach as songs and poems. Songs can develop a special interest and motivation of junior school students is learning English language. The song is a valuable educational material that develops not only verbal skills, but also the creative and informative abilities of the junior school students. An easy and relaxed method will help to quickly memorize new words and grammar building. A good song improves the mood and helps to relax or, on the contrary, to energize.

Keywords: junior school students, poetic texts, songs, psychological features, foreign languages, mother tongue, musical culture, listening, poems.

In the era of globalization, this today focuses on a renewed educational channel, general education institutions aim at improving the quality of the teaching process and the effectiveness of English acquisition. In the 20th century, linguistics, psychology, methodology and didactics have solved a number of common problems related to each other in teaching and mastering English by junior school students of different ages and educational levels. Although some words and phrases are easy to remember in the process of learning English, some words require special exercises in order to master them.

Since the growing personality in the conditions of humanization of education is at the centre of all educational activities, the search for effective ways and methods of teaching, including English language teaching, attracts the attention of many scientists, methodologists and teachers. One of these effective teaching methods is the role of songs and poems in English lessons.

Almost all teachers and pedagogues working with junior school students at different stages of learning attach great importance to songs and poems when teaching English. Some teaching aids are based entirely on the use of poems. They can be either in the original or in an especially collected sample.

The issue of the use of verse and song in education has been of concern to people since ancient times. Historians say that in the schools of ancient Greece many texts were learned by singing, and in elementary classes in India the alphabet and arithmetic were already learned by singing.

The relevance of this topic is due to the fact that currently certain methodological aspects of using English-American poetry in English lessons are analyzed in

the pages of some professional journals, there is not general concept of using songs and poems in teaching English to junior school students in general education institutions. It is important that this concept is analyzed and studied, as the aim of English language teaching is not only to gain knowledge, form skills and abilities of junior school students, but also to comprehensively master the linguistic and cultural information of a particular country. The junior school students will also be able to learn the cultural and aesthetic character of another country, the values of the national culture through examples of poems and songwriting. In English lessons, teachers may often ignore poems and songs. And when using them, they resort only to traditional works, which in turn causes junior school students to be indifferent to poems and verses. Another problem is that for many teachers all work with a song (poem) is done only at the level of «listening» and «learning», so junior school students often do not understand the meaning of the song or poem they have memorized. It follows that in practice insufficient attention is paid to the use of poems and songs in English lessons.

The age of elementary classes is considered between 7 and 9 years old. This is relatively the age of physical development of junior school students. Teaching of English at an early stage is based on psychological features of junior school students such as: plasticity of natural mechanisms of mastering speech, intensive formation of cognitive processes, ability to quickly memorize, analyze language information and systematize speech flows in different languages, absence of language barrier (fear), etc. Scientists and psychologists believe that junior students should start learning Eng-

lish at early years [1; p. 3]. In elementary classes a junior school student is psychologically ready to consciously learn English materials. The plasticity of the natural mechanism of language acquisition allows the junior school students to successfully master English in appropriate conditions.

It is better to start learning English from the age of 7-8, when the junior school students have a good command of the mother tongue and is aware and understanding of the new language. Junior school students at this age easily remember small language materials and reproduce them well. At this age, there should be a change in the leading activity, i.e. a transition from play activities to learning. However, play retains its leading role junior school students continue to play. Consequently, the opportunity to rely on play activities allows for a natural motivation to speak English and makes the simplest statements interesting and meaningful.

At an early school age, a junior school student's command of English, his or her speaking ability and the broadening of his or her general outlook have a beneficial effect on the junior school student's overall psychological development. The junior school student learns about the world around him/her through his/her mother tongue and foreign languages. This helps to form his positive motivation to learn English in the later stages of schooling at an early stage [2; p. 7].

Junior school students have a fairly well-developed memory and can memorize randomly, but this skill is not fully practiced. They can remember easily what is particularly affecting them, which is in line with their personal interests. With this age in mind, the teacher organizes teaching the students to use the lexico-grammatical material in situations that are related to their interests and that allow them to create motives for communication, interaction between the junior school students as well as speech exercises.

Memorizing poems, verses, songs, not only strengthens the junior school students' memory but also opens up great opportunities to increase the vocabulary. But the teacher needs to systematically introduce the vocabulary units learned in the lesson and always encourage junior school students who use these vocabulary units during the lesson. Vocabulary acquisition occurs through the development of automatic skills, due to repeated daily listening and reproduction of words and turns of speech in the process of communication [3; p. 12]. For example, instead of a simple greeting before you start each day, you can start with poems that teach how to greet in English. In the first stage, you can use words that explain the meaning of phrases with junior school students and help them understand what is being said.

The use of songs in the target language is relevant at the initial stage of English learning. Junior school students will be exposed to the culture of the country that first became a speaker of the target language, as, according to psychologists, junior school students working with this type of linguo-cultural material, perceive foreign cultures with a special sensitivity. In this way, the prerequisites for the all-round development of the pupil's personality in primary class are created, as

specially processed songs awaken imaginative thinking and form taste.

Introducing junior school students to the cultural heritage and spiritual values of themselves and other nations can be successfully addressed by using songs and poems in the process of learning English. The use of musical, in particular light, meaningful songs, poetic poems built in an easy language, which are a true example of creativity [4; p. 23], is of significant help in this regard.

The song genre, as one of the most important genres of music, is able, thanks to the presence of verbal text, to reflect accurately and figuratively in the language studied the diversity of social life in the country; it influences the child's intellect, emotions and visual and artistic memory and contributes to the aesthetic education of junior school students. The use of song material stimulates motivation in junior school students and, consequently, promotes better absorption of language material under the influence of involuntary memorization mechanisms, allowing for an increase in the child's learning of the language. The song is an example of the sound of English speech as well as a carrier of cultural information. Leading thinkers and educators of past eras have always ensured that the art of singing has a definite place in the education of the younger generation. K. D. Ushinsky believed that joint singing at school is a powerful pedagogical tool which organizes, unites, educates junior school students towards cooperation [5; p. 9].

The song is an exceptionally effective method, the most adequate authentic material, built on the psychological and pedagogical features of teaching English in the elementary classes. But the well-established stereotype that the effectiveness of teaching English with the help of a song can be achieved only in the elementary classes is false. Today it is proven that the psychological and pedagogical value of the song method is necessary in both middle and high school. The sound of the music, the subtle melody and the text of the song itself, and its performance suggest a free and rapid assimilation of the text by the higher school students. The lyrics help to learn the language as a system as well as to familiarize the learners with the mentality and culture of the country of the target language. The timing of the text of the song is determined by the conditions set by the teacher and the junior school students' level of learning. In this case, the aims can be represented as the acquisition of vocabulary as well as the development of grammatical structures, skills and attitudes. Consequently, the use of the song method in teaching English language to junior school students will help them to engage more easily with the culture of the English. The melody of the song should meet the interests and hobbies of the learners, the content of which should carry a semantic weight [6; p. 23].

Having considered all of the above, it can be noted that the achievement of the necessary level of knowledge, abilities, skills set for junior school students in accordance with their pedagogical and psychological features in teaching English, is implemented by many methods, one of which is the method of working with poetic works - poems, verses in English lessons.

However, it should be noted that many methodologists in this case recommend that junior school students divide the poetic material into "themes" so that they gradually assimilate the lexical material.

The pedagogical approach of the role of song and poems in teaching English in elementary classes are as follows:

- Firstly, poems, songs are junior school students' favorite and interesting textual material, so working with them gives the junior student a positive emotional response and greatly facilitates the absorption of this material.

- Secondly, authentic literary or folklore material facilitates the understanding of language in the context of cultures.

- Thirdly, poetic texts and songs are excellent material for practicing rhythm and intonation of English language and improving pronunciation.

- Fourthly, when working with poems, songs solve the problem of repetition of pronunciation from one pattern or perception of one word.

- By giving junior school students communicative tasks, it is possible to achieve not only their perception of the topic, but also the goal of the lesson [7; p. 14].

Thus, the role of songs and poems in the teaching of English in the elementary classes develops the junior school students' sense of beauty and their poetic and musical choice. At the same time a musical hearing is developed. It has been observed that junior school students who listen well to music, usually a good grasp of English language. In lessons and extracurricular activities, junior school students are exposed to poetic and musical culture (classical poetry, folklore) and, although the works are not at a very high level (popular

music), they receive lexical and grammatical information performed by native speakers. When working with melodic and melodic texts it is necessary to ensure that junior school students enjoy themselves without overloading them with tasks and exercises. In junior school, it is better not to insist on memorizing texts, but to offer to memorize the text of a song or poem in class during English lessons.

References

1. The English language // Learn and play in English lessons. Grades 2-4. Moscow: Drofa, 2003.
2. English poems for children // Compiled by. V.A. Verkhoglyad - M.: Rolf, 2001.
3. Barkhaev, B.P. Pedagogical psychology: textbook for universities / B.P. Barkhaev. - Vocational psychology: a textbook for higher school / B.P. Barkhaev. - SPb: Peter, 2009. - 444 c.
4. Baryshnikov N.V. Methodology of Second Foreign Language Teaching at School. - Moscow: Prosveshcheniye, 2003. - 159 c.
5. Bychkovskaya E.V. The Development of Foreign Language Interest in Younger Students / E.V. Bychkovskaya, A.L. Goncharenko // Foreign Language at School - 2008. - № 1. - p.51-53.
6. Galskova N.D., Gez N.I. Theory of teaching foreign languages. Linguodidactics and Methodology: Textbook. 5-th revised edition. - M.: Academy IC, 2008. - 334 c.
7. Shatskikh E. English in verses and pictures. Rhyming texts for the accumulation and consolidation of vocabulary in primary school / E. Shatskikh. - M., 2006. - 32p.: ill. - (Library of "First September", series "English language"; 2 / 2006).